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Towards Zero Emissions Buildings – A multi-criteria assessment of a timber-framed prefabricated façade solution incorporating bio-based materials

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Abstract. The construction sector increasingly adopts off-site prefabricated systems for deep retrofitting, reducing waste while enabling fast and customizable solutions. When combined with efficient heating, ventilation and air conditioning (HVAC) systems and renewable energy sources (RES), off-site prefabricated envelope components have occurred as a powerful strategy for achieving Nearly Zero Energy Buildings (NZEB). However, alongside the anticipated improvements in energy performance, there is an emerging need to comprehensively assess the environmental footprint of these energy retrofits. In this context, the concept of Zero Emission Buildings (ZEB) is evolving as a progression of the NZEB framework within European Union policies, with a focus on both operational efficiency and the use of low embodied carbon materials. This study examines a timber-framed prefabricated façade panel for the deep renovation of a residential building in Berlin, coupled with energy efficient systems to meet ZEB standards. The aim is to select the optimal insulation material through a multi-criteria analysis in terms of sustainability metrics, economic viability, and indoor environmental quality. The analysis assesses energy savings achieved through the decreased heat loss and the improved HVAC efficiency. Besides, a Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) is conducted to quantify the embodied carbon of the retrofitting components covering the product stage (A1-A3), the end-of-life stage (C1-C4) and the operational energy use (B6). Additionally, Life Cycle Cost (LCC) and thermal comfort indexes are calculated for each scenario. The results indicate that the proposed bio-based façade panel offers an optimal solution, significantly reducing total energy consumption and supports ZEB targets. Although the retrofit's initial embodied energy is significant, the amount of operational energy savings offset this over time.

Keywords: Zero Emission Buildings, Prefabricated façade panel, Embodied carbon, Multi-criteria analysis

1. Introduction

In the European energy landscape, the residential sector remains a dominant contributor to energy consumption and greenhouse gas emissions, consuming approximately 26% of total energy within the European Union (EU). A notable 80% of this is attributed to heating, cooling, and domestic hot water consumption. The EU Building Stock Observatory reveals that most

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residential buildings were constructed before the implementation of national thermal standards, resulting in poorly insulated façade [1]. The slow renovation rate of existing buildings exacerbates the challenge of attaining the EU energy targets [2].

Deep energy retrofitting utilizing prefabricated facade solutions has emerged as a transformative strategy to address these challenges. Prefabrication offers numerous advantages, including rapid installation, high quality control, and reduced on-site disruption, aligning with the construction sector's broader shift toward industrialized methods. By integrating energy-efficient HVAC systems, renewable energy sources, and multifunctional envelope components, these solutions provide a pathway toward achieving NZEB standards [3].

The construction sector is shifting beyond NZEB toward the realization of zero-emissions buildings (ZEB), emphasizing the need for standardized definitions and assessment methods [4]. Carbon-neutral buildings aim to eliminate greenhouse gas emissions through a combination of operational energy efficiency [5], embodied carbon reductions, and renewable energy integration. The integration of bio-based materials into prefabricated retrofitting solutions further enhances the environmental and economic performance of the solution. Bio-based materials such as wood fiber, hemp and straw or sheep wool (animal-based) are characterized for their carbon storage potential contributing to a decarbonized building stock [6], [7].

This study contributes to the evolving ZEB framework by assessing SmartWall, a prefabricated timber-framed facade panel with integrated HVAC systems and high-performance windows, introduced in Katsigiannis et al. [8]. Various scenarios are examined for its insulation layer, comparing bio-based, mineral-based and high-performance insulation materials. A three-phase framework has been followed to assess each scenario. First, a building-level assessment (via TRNSYS) that quantifies the operational energy need and the thermal comfort conditions for each of the retrofitted options. In the second phase, the carbon footprint of each scenario is assessed by calculating both the embodied carbon and operational emissions using an LCA (via OneClickLCA). On top of that, life-long expenditures are assumed for each scenario to perform LCC calculations. Finally, the holistic evaluation of the proposed scenarios is conducted through a multi-criteria assessment method (PROMETHEE), which encompasses three key dimensions: sustainability, economic performance, and indoor environmental quality.

2. Case study

2.1. SmartWall description

SmartWall is a multifunctional retrofitting system featuring prefabricated timber-framed walls with integrated insulation, a slim-type fan coil for heating and cooling, and high-performance windows. Photovoltaics can be mounted externally on the façade or the roof. It can be installed externally or internally, depending on space and aesthetic requirements.

As a modular “Plug and Play” panel, SmartWall includes flexible piping and electrical wiring for seamless integration with existing or new HVAC and electrical systems, minimizing on-site installation time. The insulated façade panel features triple-pane low-e windows with mechanical ventilation and heat recovery. The wood-aluminum frame ($U_f=1.4 \text{ W}/(\text{m}^2\cdot\text{K})$), and triple Argon-filled glazing ($U_g=0.58 \text{ W}/(\text{m}^2\cdot\text{K})$) result in a window thermal transmittance of $U_w=0.89 \text{ W}/(\text{m}^2\cdot\text{K})$.

The layer materials are anchored on a timber frame, completed by OSB, weatherboard, and a ventilated layer. Three insulation types are examined: mineral based, high-performance (VIP), and bio-based materials. Since the fan coil unit occupies a significant portion of the insulation layer, a 20 mm Vacuum Insulation Panel (VIP) is installed in the rear side to ensure a consistent thermal transmittance across the SmartWall.

In the examined case, SmartWall is paired with a low-temperature air-to-water heat pump for heating and domestic hot water supply. The integrated slim-type fan coil distributes conditioned air within each room. Domestic hot water production is supported by a 3.2 m² vacuum solar panel, while a 20 m² rooftop photovoltaic system generates electricity (Figure 2).

Figure 1. Overview of SmartWall panel

2.2. Demo case

The examined building is a detached single-family house constructed in 1965, located in southern Berlin. It consists of a two-story main body with a mono-pitch roof, two single-story side extensions, and an unheated basement. In its unrenovated state, it is classified as Energy Class F according to national energy performance certification standards.

Figure 2. SmartWall combined with auxiliary system

Figure 3. Renovated state with SmartWall panels (drawings and 3D model)

Beyond the SmartWall installation on external masonry, additional insulation is applied to one roof level ($U=0.06 \text{ W}/(\text{m}^2\text{K})$) and a green roof ($U=0.13 \text{ W}/(\text{m}^2\text{K})$). Furthermore, the PV modules offset electricity costs and enhance energy independence.

The renovated structure is depicted in Figure 3, with general information and occupant profiles summarized in the following table. During the cooling period, natural ventilation is configured for thermal comfort, while the hourly DHW load profile follows ASHRAE 90.1.

Table 1. Building geometrical and operational characteristics

Description		Operation	
Gross Floor Area	284 m ²	Occupants	6
External Wall Area	279 m ²		
Windows opening Area	59 m ²	Lighting	6.4 W/m ²
Windows to Wall Ratio	21%		
Gross Roof Area	176 m ²		

Description		Operation	
Total Volume	786 m ³ ₂	Electrical devices	4 W/m ²
Ventilation	0.4 h ⁻¹		

3. Methodology

The methodology followed aims to evaluate the primary insulation layer of the SmartWall panel, examining bio-based (wood fiber, straw, hemp and sheep wool), mineral-based (perlite and stone wool) and high performance (VIP) materials. As the insulation material is the sole varying parameter, while key characteristics such as U-value remain comparable, each scenario is considered functionally equivalent, enabling a fair and consistent comparison. Each alternative is assessed in terms of energy performance, LCA, LCC and thermal comfort, while the optimum case is selected through a multicriteria analysis. The examined scenarios are summarized in Table 2.

3.1. Energy performance

The component-level thermal performance of each wall panel was evaluated using COMSOL Multiphysics, accounting for thermal bridges through a steady-state analysis, following ISO 10211:2007. The thermal transmittance of SmartWall panels for each examined insulation option is presented in Table 2. Thicknesses were set per manufacturer specifications to achieve U-values ranging from 0.15 to 0.17 W/m²K. The VIP achieves the lowest U-value by ca. 10% while requiring about 75% less insulation thickness.

Table 2. Assessed insulation materials, U-values (including thermal-bridges) and costs for each wall panel

Column heading	Wood fiber	Rice straw	Expanded perlite	Stone wool	Sheep wool	Hemp	VIP
Thickness (mm)	240	240	240	240	240	240	60
Cost [€/m ²]	24,25	10,00	38,90	29,80	59,02	33,50	366,67
U [W/m ² K]	0.173	0.169	0.173	0.163	0.169	0.170	0.153

Regarding the building-level analysis, different scenarios are simulated in TRNSYS using a common geometry (Figure 3) and HVAC systems to evaluate the energy impact of SmartWall components. Annual simulations incorporate Berlin climate data from the Meteororm database. Each room is treated as an independent thermal zone with thermostatic heating control set at 20°C, while cooling needs are negligible and are primarily addressed through ventilation.

The TRNSYS model (Figure 4) includes three main segments for active systems. The building unit defines geometry, operation, and element characteristics. Heating is provided by a variable-speed 2-pipe fan coil unit (2.18 kW) per zone, controlled by a thermostat and supplied by an air-to-water heat pump (9.37 kW) that also supplies DHW.

A 300 L tank stores hot water, reducing start-stops and improving efficiency. DHW is supplied by another 300 L tank heated by both an evacuated tube solar collector and the heat pump. DHW control combines a forced hourly profile with thermostatic regulation, adjusting temperature seasonally.

A PV array models power generation, with options for monocrystalline, polycrystalline, or thin-film panels, and a maximum power point tracker (MPPT). Ten high-performance PV modules (20 m²) are connected in series. An inverter converts DC to AC, supplying the load or feeding excess power to the grid under a net-metering regime.

The final, yearly, electrical energy (FE) need for space heating and DHW, calculated through the TRNSYS simulation, serves as the energy performance KPI.

$$FE = E_{el,SpaceHeating} + E_{el,DHW} \quad [kWh_{el}/y] \quad (1)$$

Figure 4. SmartWall system modelled in TRNSYS studio

3.2. Life cycle analysis (LCA)

The LCA approach applied, calculates the embodied carbon of the renovation solution for each insulation alternative. Meaning that the pool of materials refers to the envelope panels, including construction and mechanical equipment. Given the use of bio-based materials, biogenic carbon mitigation is factored in, including biogenic uptake, manufacturing emissions, and carbon storage. To better facilitate the multicriteria analysis, the carbon storage is not assessed separately, but according to EN 15804+A1/+A2, adopting an A1-A3 + C system boundary, while ensuring compliance with European environmental performance standards. More specifically, following this methodology, the negative carbon uptake is considered in stages A1-A3 and the positive release of CO₂ in stage C as balancing biogenic waste disposal.

The input of the carbon assessment is framed with several assumptions based on available data and study scope. Service life estimates follow technical specifications of materials and systems, using Environmental Product Declarations (EPDs) when available. Material transportation distances within Europe are considered for a localized logistics approach. Emissions associated with material production, particularly those related to grid electricity, are adapted to European energy standards. For the operational phase, Germany's 2022 electricity mix from the ÖKOBAUDAT platform is used.

The material inventory (**Table 3**) for embodied energy calculations considers only components added due to renovation, excluding pre-renovation elements. Primary data and design are sourced from SmartWall developer by AMSolutions [9].

Table 3. Aggregated material inventory for capital infrastructure

Infrastructure		Systems (fan coil, heat pump & PV)	
SmartWall material	Weight (kg)	SmartWall material	Weight (kg)
Clay Plaster	2855.9	Metal Sheet (Fan Coil)	270
Climate board	2124.9	Reinforcing steel	120
OSB	4501.5	Copper	35.2
Wood fibre insulation	6055.2	Steel, low alloyed	32
Straw panel	4642.5	Tube insulation	16
Perlite panel	9285	Lubricating oil	2.7

Infrastructure		Systems (fan coil, heat pump & PV)	
SmartWall material	Weight (kg)	SmartWall material	Weight (kg)
Stone wool	6406.6	Hot Water buffer tank	139
Sheep wool	1671.3	Tubular solar panel	3.2 (m ²)
Hemp panel	3714	PV panels	20 (m ²)
Vacuum Panel	4201.4	Three-phase inverter	-
Weather/soft wood fibre board	3131.4	Air/water Heat Pump	-
Fleece	1054.5	VIP	34.41
Drainage layer	4218.2		
Root resistant membrane	249.4		

Alongside product-stage and end-of-life environmental impacts, operational energy use (B6) from the energy assessment is included. The carbon footprint (GWP) of the operational state of the building serves as the comparative LCA performance indicator, expressed in the annual amount of kgCO₂e. The calculations are summarized by the following equation:

$$GWP = \frac{(TE_{SH} + TE_{DHW}) \cdot GEF_{el} - TE_p \cdot GEF_{gen}}{A} \quad [\text{kgCO}_2\text{eq}] \quad (2)$$

Where TE_{SH} and TE_{DHW} are the space heating and DHW energy consumption per year [kWh/year], while GEF_{el} and GEF_{gen} are the predetermined conversion factors of carbon emissions occurred from electricity consumption and on-site generation respectively [kgCO₂eq/kWh_{el}].

3.3. Life cycle cost (LCC)

The Life Cycle Cost (LCC) methodology assesses the total costs of insulation alternatives in a deep renovation over a 50-year study period (SP). In accordance with ISO 15686-5, the analysis incorporates a discount rate (r) of 3.1% assuming a renovated wall area of 279 m². The cost assessment includes initial investment, operational and maintenance expenses, periodic replacements, and residual values. Since alternatives have similar maintenance, replacement, and residual costs, differences lie mainly in initial and operational expenses. Initial costs cover insulation material (Table 2), assembly, transportation, and installation, while operational costs stem from annual energy consumption for space heating and DHW.

$$LCC = \text{Initial cost} + \sum_{t=0}^{SP=50} \frac{\text{Operational} + \text{Replacement cost}}{(1+r)^t} \quad [€] \quad (3)$$

A discounted cash flow analysis ensures future costs are expressed as present values, allowing for a comprehensive economic performance evaluation to support informed decision-making.

3.4. Thermal comfort

Occupants satisfaction is assessed based on indoor thermal conditions with thermal comfort levels estimated using the Predicted Mean Vote (PMV) index calculated through TRNSYS simulations. As performance indicator, thermal discomfort hours (TDH) are quantified by calculating the total number of hours within a year during which the absolute value of PMV exceeds 0.7, the threshold defining the Class-C comfort level according to ISO 7730 [10].

$$TDH = \sum_{i=1}^{8760} \tau_i \quad [\text{hours}] \quad (4)$$

3.5. Multicriteria method (PROMETHEE)

Among advanced ranking methods, the Preference Ranking Organization Method for Enrichment Evaluation (PROMETHEE) proves effective for selecting among a finite set of alternatives. PROMETHEE II stands out for its simplicity and ability to resolve conflicts between criteria, providing a comprehensive ranking. Using pairwise comparisons, it structures preferences through a normalized decision matrix containing Key Performance Indicators (KPIs).

The initial step involves normalizing the decision matrix, containing the Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) values, denoted as x_{ij} , for each examined alternative. In this evaluation, all criteria are non-beneficial, meaning the optimal solution has the lowest indicator value. After computing these criteria, evaluative differences ($x_{ik}-x_{jk}$) are determined, leading to the preference function. PROMETHEE assigns each alternative a positive outranking flow ($\Phi^+(x_i)$), indicating relative strength and a negative flow ($\Phi^-(x_i)$), representing how much it is outranked. The net outranking flow, obtained by subtracting the two, determines the final ranking, with higher values indicating better alternatives.

The multicriteria analysis considers four factors: energy consumption, life cycle assessment (LCA), life cycle cost (LCC), and thermal discomfort hours (TDH). Two weighting scenarios are used: an isobaric approach (equal importance) and one based on a stakeholder questionnaire from occupants, contractors, and engineers. The responses highlight a preference for economic factors, with energy performance slightly prioritized over the remaining two criteria (Table 4).

Table 4. Different criteria weight scenarios

Weight scenarios	W_{energy}	$W_{\text{environmental}}$	W_{cost}	$W_{\text{thermal comfort}}$
Isobaric	0.25	0.25	0.25	0.25
Questionnaire	0.227	0.187	0.413	0.174

4. Results and discussion

Seven alternatives were evaluated based on four key criteria: energy consumption, LCA, LCC and thermal discomfort hours (TDH), all minimized for optimal performance. A multicriteria analysis using the PROMETHEE method was conducted under two weighting scenarios: equal weighting (isobaric) and a stakeholder preference-based ranking.

Energy performance (Figure 5) correlates with thermal transmittance (U-value) of the wall panels, as expected. Materials with lower thermal conductivity, such as VIP (0.093 W/mK) and Stone Wool (0.115 W/mK), demonstrate superior efficiency, consuming 9,173 kWh and 9,296 kWh annually, respectively. Conversely, materials with higher thermal conductivity, like Expanded Perlite (0.129 W/mK), exhibit increased energy consumption, reaching 9,366 kWh.

Figure 5. Total energy consumed for heating and DHW in electrical kWh

LCA results (Figure 6) illustrate the Global Warming Potential (GWP) of each insulation material, considering the carbon footprint and the operational energy emissions. Notably, while most of the alternatives (except perlite and VIP panel) present a roughly similar environmental performance, the straw panel insulation exhibits the lowest GWP (298,911 kg CO₂e). It is worth mentioning that biogenic insulation materials like straw, wood fiber, hemp, and sheep wool sequester carbon during production but release it at end-of-life, creating a temporary carbon storage effect. Wood fiber and hemp show the strongest biogenic dynamics, unlike mineral or synthetic insulations, which lack carbon sequestration and have consistently higher greenhouse gas emissions. The substantial contribution of operational energy across all alternatives underscores the importance of selecting materials with superior thermal performance to mitigate long-term carbon emissions. However, despite its enhanced energy efficiency, VIP insulation fails to offset its significantly higher embodied carbon footprint, resulting in the highest GWP at 330,455 kg CO₂e.

Aggregated impact of embodied carbon and energy consumption

Figure 6. LCA results (A1-A3, B6 & C1-C4 stages) in kgCO₂e

The LCC analysis involves estimating fluctuating prices. However, any variations in these values will affect all seven alternatives proportionally, maintaining their relative ranking. Results show minimal discrepancies among the options, primarily due to differences in initial costs.

Life Cycle Cost (LCC)

Figure 7. Total cost from LCC assessment with stacked spending categories

As illustrated in Figure 7, bio-based and mineral-based insulation materials are significantly more cost-effective than high-performance alternatives like VIP. While most bio-based options have similar LCC values, rice straw is the most economical at €108,296. In contrast, despite the lower operational cost due to superior energy efficiency, VIP's high initial investment results in the highest LCC, which is nearly twice that of the rice straw panel.

Thermal discomfort hours (TDH) values follow a similar trend to U-values, reinforcing the connection between insulation performance and thermal comfort. VIP insulation achieves the lowest TDH at 864 hours annually, followed closely by wood fibre board and stone wool. Hemp insulation, with the highest TDH at 954 hours, demonstrates the least favorable thermal comfort.

The Multicriteria Analysis, conducted using the PROMETHEE method, provides a comparative ranking of insulation materials based on two different weighting scenarios. Under the isobaric approach, which assigns equal importance to all criteria, rice straw emerges as the best-performing insulation, followed by stone wool and wood fibre board. Expanded perlite ranks last due to its high energy consumption and significant environmental impact. When criteria weights are derived from the stakeholder questionnaire, which places greater emphasis on economic factors and slightly prioritizes energy performance over the other two criteria, the rankings shift slightly. Notably, VIP drops to the last position, reflecting its unfavorable balance between cost, environmental impact, and performance according to expert judgment. Meanwhile, rice straw, stone wool and wood fibre board retain the three top ranks respectively, reaffirming their balanced performance across all criteria.

Table 5. Multi-criteria analysis results – Alternatives ranking

Insulation material	Energy consumption (kWh/a·m ²)	LCA (kgCO _{2eq})	LCC (€)	Thermal discomfort hours (h)	Ranking isobaric	Ranking questionnaire
Wood fibre board	9,354	251,782	112,607	901	3	3
Rice straw	9,316	271,530	108,296	903	1	1
Expanded perlite	9,366	300,144	116,801	928	7	6
Stone wool	9,296	281,420	113,643	909	2	2
Sheep wool	9,322	277,354	122,025	933	4	4
Hemp	9,356	261,689	115,206	954	6	5
VIP	9,173	308,629	206,543	864	5	7

This analysis underscores that bio-based materials used as insulation layers are not only competitive but may also be preferred over conventional or high-performance alternatives such as expanded perlite and VIP. Namely, rice straw, stone wool and wood fibre board consistently perform well, making them the most attractive insulation choices. Conversely, even though VIP offers notable thermal advantages, its high embodied carbon footprint and life cycle cost significantly diminish its overall desirability when multiple factors are considered. Despite that, a sensitivity or uncertainty analysis is not included, thus variations in insulation-related parameters, such as thermal properties, embodied emissions, and cost, may affect the robustness of the ranking. Although all other inputs were held constant, future research should explore the influence of such uncertainties to strengthen the reliability of comparative assessments.

5. Conclusion

This study evaluated seven insulation materials based on energy consumption, life cycle assessment (LCA), life cycle cost (LCC), and thermal discomfort hours (TDH), utilizing the PROMETHEE multicriteria analysis method. The findings highlight bio-based materials, particularly wood fibre board and rice straw, as well-balanced options across environmental, economic, and thermal comfort criteria, making them highly appealing alternatives.

In terms of energy efficiency, VIP and stone wool demonstrate the best performance due to their low U-values, leading to reduced annual energy consumption. However, VIP's advantages in

thermal performance fail to counteract its significantly higher embodied carbon footprint and life cycle cost, ultimately making it the least favorable choice when considering multiple sustainability factors. The LCA results further emphasize the importance of embodied carbon, with rice straw exhibiting the lowest GWP, reinforcing its strong environmental profile.

Cost analysis reveals that bio-based materials offer the most economically viable solutions, with rice straw achieving the lowest LCC. Despite VIP's reduced operational costs, its prohibitively high initial investment renders it the most expensive option. Thermal comfort results align with insulation performance, with VIP, stone wool, and wood fibre board providing the lowest TDH values.

The multicriteria analysis confirms that rice straw, stone wool and wood fibre board consistently rank among the top choices, while expanded perlite and VIP rank lowest due to their respective shortcomings in cost and environmental impact. Ultimately, this study underscores the viability of bio-based insulation materials, positioning them as both competitive and sustainable alternatives to conventional and high-performance solutions.

While the analysis provides valuable insights, potential uncertainties in insulation-related parameters were not examined, warranting further investigation.

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